

can only occur in borderline cases. It should eventually improve data processing and interpretation.

To apply this method, estimate the

exact area of the plot and then the area of azolla cover. First ask: "Does azolla cover more or less than 50% of the area?" Continue to estimate

according to the scale. The same scale (except for level 6) can be used to estimate area covered by rice and by different weed species. □

Urea timing and application method in direct-seeded lowland rice

P.K. Mahapatra, K. Maity, and D. Lenka, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar 751003, Orissa, India

A trial tested time and method of applying urea N on waterlogged (up to 50 cm submergence) direct-seeded rice during the 1984 and 1985 wet seasons under rainfed conditions. OR117-8 (160 d) seed was broadcast on sandy clay loam (pH 5.1, 0.045% total N, 7 kg Olsen P/ha, and 50 kg K/ha). At sowing, 11 kg P/ha and 21 kg K/ha were applied uniformly. N as urea was applied at 50 kg/ha (see table).

Cured urea was prepared by mixing prilled urea 1:5 with moist soil and incubating 48 h in the shade. The rate of cured urea N was based on N added to the moist soil. When sufficient

Effect of urea and cured urea on grain yield of rice, Bhubaneswar, India.

Treatment ^a	Yield (t/ha)		
	1984	1985	Mean
Control (no N)	3.3	2.6	2.9
100% N at seeding as PU	4.0	4.1	4.0
100% N at seeding as CU	4.3	3.7	4.0
50% N as PU at seeding + 50% N as PU through spray	4.0	3.6	3.8
50% N as CU at seeding + 50% N as PU through spray	3.9	3.2	3.5
50% N as PU at seeding + 25% at 30 DAS + 25% at panicle initiation (PI)	4.4	3.7	4.0
50% N as CU at seeding + 25% at 30 DAS + 25% at PI	4.1	3.6	3.8
50% N as PU at 40 DAS + 25% at 61 DAS + 25% at PI	5.0	4.5	4.1
50% N at CU at 40 DAS + 25% at 61 DAS + 25% at PI	4.4	3.1	4.0
CD (0.05)	0.6	0.7	-

^a PU = prilled urea, CU = cured urea.

rainwater became available, the seedbed was plowed down by a wooden country plow followed by planking (a common practice in Orissa) at 30 d after sowing (DAS). Weeding and gapfilling were done at 40 DAS.

Application of 50% N at 40 DAS plus 25% at 61 DAS and 25% at panicle initiation gave the highest grain yield in both years. Applying 100% N as urea at seeding gave consistently good yields. Cured urea proved to be inferior to prilled urea. □

An improved method of representative sampling from aerobic soil solutions

D.K. Kundu, F.N. Ponnampereuma, and H. U. Neue, Soil Chemistry Department, IRRRI

Analysis of a soil solution collected in situ from aerobic soil can be used for soil chemical environment analyses. However, it is difficult to obtain a sample from aerobic soils with moisture contents near field capacity (FC). The displacement method for well-packed FC moist soil columns has not been tested for validity under normal pot culture conditions. We evaluated samples collected by the conventional displacement method from three FC potted soils with different densities.

Twelve kilograms each of air-dried

(>2 mm sized) Luisiana clay, Maahas clay, and Pila loam soils were placed in 16-liter porcelain pots fitted at the bottom with drainage (coarse sintered glass) tubes. The soils were brought to FC moisture using tensiometers.

To collect soil solutions, 0.5% KSCN as displacing solution was poured on the soil surfaces. The displaced solutions were drained into measuring cylinders. We tested the collected solutions for SCN-ion at regular intervals. Drops of acidic FeCl₃ solution were used as the indicator (a blood red-colored complex is formed).

From the fast-draining Luisiana clay and Pila loam soils, we could collect only 20-30 ml of soil solution. Beyond this volume, the leachate was diluted by the displacement solution. In slow-draining Maahas clay, no displacement fluid appeared in the first 200 ml.

About 175 ml of soil solution is needed for a complete analysis; the displacement method was not appropriate for soils with fast drainage properties.

In a second experiment, we compared soil solution collected by the displacement method with equilibrated saturation extracts of three soils. Equilibrium was ensured by recycling the saturation extracts three times. Saturating a soil to FC, then immediately draining it does not give equilibrium extract. Allowing FC soils to remain saturated for a long time (beyond 8 h in many cases) might cause soil reduction.

We used three soils set up as in the first experiment, replicated six times. Demineralized water, in volumes required to bring the FC soils to saturation, was poured on the soil surface. The first 125-ml leachates

were collected as the displacement solutions, and the rest as saturation extract.

The extracts were then recycled through soils three times, first allowing them to remain in contact with soil for about 30 min by keeping the drain tube closed. The final (fourth) extract was collected as the equilibrated saturation extract. To prevent further oxidation, the soil solutions were collected in flasks prefilled with N₂ gas.

We measured solution pH and Eh in an electrometric cell under N₂ environment. The recycled saturation extracts were representative of soil

Comparison of pH and Eh values^a of solutions from FC moist soils collected by 2 different methods.

Soil	Soil pH (1:1)	pH		Eh (V)	
		Displaced solution	Recycled saturation extract	Displaced solution	Recycled saturation extract
Luisiana clay	4.7	4.6 a	4.5 a	0.31 b	0.32 b
UK-1 clay loam	6.6	5.9 b	6.5 b	0.29 a	0.26 a
Pila loam	7.5	6.9 b	7.3 b	0.27 a	0.23 a

^aMean of 6 replications. In a row, treatment means of a given parameter having a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at 5% level.

solutions; the displacement solutions were seriously diluted and altered by the displacing liquid (demineralized water, pH 5.38) (see table). During subsequent experiments, we

observed that it is necessary to recycle fast-draining soils three times; recycling once or twice seldom ensured equilibrium. □

Environment and its Influence

Forecasting tungro (RTV) epidemic in Tamil Nadu

P. Vidhyasekaran and H.D. Lewin, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute (TRRI), Aduthurai 612101, India

Sporadic RTV epidemics have been reported in several countries. In Tamil Nadu, the disease occurred in 1978, 1979, 1980, 1981, and 1984, but not in 1977, 1982, 1983, and 1985.

RTV can be controlled by timely application of insecticides to check the vector population. But in a non-epidemic year, preventive insecticides are wasted.

Only young rice plants are highly RTV susceptible; infection 45 d after sowing normally does not result in economic loss. A system to forecast possible epidemic RTV outbreak is needed.

We monitored light trap catches of the vector green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* population for 9 yr (1977-85) and attempted to correlate weather factors with disease and vector incidence.

The vector population started increasing in mid-Aug, reached its peak between mid-Sep and early Oct, then

declined. Highly susceptible rice cultivar TN1 was planted at 2-wk intervals from Jul to Dec. RTV was severe in Sep and Oct; crops sown in the first 2 wk of Sep recorded maximum incidence. The period favorable to vector multiplication and RTV incidence was Sep-Oct.

The 9-yr weather data for Aug-Nov were analyzed critically. No significant difference in maximum and minimum temperatures was found between RTV epidemic and non-epidemic years. Rainfall and humidity patterns were also similar.

The data, however, revealed one important fact: when RTV occurred, the vector population increased (see table). This increase could be used to forecast a RTV epidemic. Vector populations during Aug cannot be taken as criteria, but population during the first 2 wk of Sep differentiated RTV epidemic and non-epidemic years. Total vector populations during Sep of epidemic and non-epidemic years were clearly distinguishable. Populations were more than 10⁵ in RTV epidemic years and around 10³ in non-epidemic years. □

RTV incidence and the vector population in Tamil Nadu during 1977-85.

Year	RTV incidence (%)	Green leafhopper ^a (no.)								Total during the season
		Aug		Sep		Oct		Nov		
		1-15	16-31	1-15	16-30	1-15	16-31	1-15	16-30	
1977	0	5	1,786	202	1,059	7,821	3,672	510	228	17,283
1978	18	175	167	3,639	20,882	92,783	143,150	7,537	584	268,917
1979	100	171	7,556	25,016	455,269	69,789	81,899	10,751	5,562	656,013
1980	40	555	4,114	49,310	53,005	148,940	21,072	148,940	21,072	447,008
1981	60	162	1,181	2,837	32,882	175,574	42,816	31,119	1,583	288,154
1982	0	1,330	2,544	1,494	2,544	7,449	1,733	343	118	16,555
1983	0	122	308	996	561	9,265	23,439	7,138	331	42,160
1984	70	1,223	1,995	106,115	15,308	33,543	6,102	168	66	164,510
1985	0	9	38	83	670	4,472	490	1,420	314	7,496
Mean		416	2,188	21,077	64,687	61,071	36,041	23,103	3,540	

^aPopulation was counted using a light trap.